

PRESSURE-RELATED ISSUES AND SELF-EFFECTIVENESS OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

JANICE A. NIÑAL

Abstract. The study determined the extent of pressure-related issues and the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public secondary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of pressure-related issues was extensive while the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for pressure-related issues have a strong positive relationship to the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of pressure-related issues on self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers: Relationships and Career Development. It was recommended that teachers should maintain a positive work outlook by responding to calls to duty with efficiency and timeliness, expressing oneself in terms of work-related challenges in order to gain administrative support and insights from colleagues, and actively participating in psychosocial wellness and professional development trainings. It is also recommended that teachers and school administrators should have a good preparation and attitude towards teaching and of their respective relationships, career development, home and work interface to avoid pressure.

KEY WORDS

1. Pressure-related issues.
2. self-effectiveness.
3. Relationships and Career Development.

1. Introduction

Pressure, especially that related to work, is found to be the second most frequent health problem. People who are in the teaching profession carry a lot of burdens. Many teachers find the demands of being a professional educator, especially in this generation, challenging. Many teachers find the demands of being a professional educator, especially in this generation, challenging. People who are in the teaching profession carry a lot of burdens. Like other types of jobs, teachers also suffer from different work stressors brought on by many factors. Additionally, they have high ambitions for their teaching. Their main strategy is to

work hard and at late hours to be as well prepared to teach as possible. They report being tired and exhausted, but at this age, they can recover during weekends and vacations, although some of the young teachers also work through the weekends. Work-related pressure is one of the most reported factors experienced by teachers that significantly affect their ability to perform their jobs. Teachers interact constantly with students, they must maintain high levels of professional performance, and they must meet goals and comply with deadlines at the same time as delivering regular curricular obligations and fulfilling other demands of the job. These are all factors that increase the stress of the professionals in this group. Pressure, itself, is an individual psychological state. It has to do with the person's perception of the work environment and the emotional experience of it. In the global perspective, according to Rafiq and Shah (2019) state that pressure has emerged across the globe as a major concern because of its high potential to cause serious damage, to not only an individual's health but his work performance as well. They added that teachers have very important roles and responsibilities in teaching and learning processes and in achieving the overall goals of education. Amongst the numerous factors having direct and serious implications for teachers' success in achieving these goals of education, the overall school environment emerges as one of the key facilitating or hindering factors. Even the best teacher fails to do well under inconvenient and unsupportive conditions. However, the teacher has numerous responsibilities including continuously upgrading their professional knowledge, motivating students, planning class activities, providing knowledge and skills to learners, maintaining discipline in the class, and keeping parents informed on their children's progress. Overall assessment of the sources of work-related pressure is perceived to be moderately affecting their teaching performance. Organizational support appeared to be closely associated with stress among teachers. It is very notable that there exists a perceived hazardous working condition. This is confounded by a lack of resources to fulfill their tasks and conflicting instructions coming from informal sources. The teachers further claimed that they experienced strict monitoring from their school administrators that manifested additional stress. High work-related stressors like time pressure, educational changes, administrative problems, educational system, professional distress, and learners' misbehavior causes among educators (Bulatevych, 2017). In the Philippines, teachers and administrators are experiencing problems like pressure. Pressure and stress problems include issues of corruption in government offices and the change of educational leadership. With its implementation, even the schools and the teachers and administrators were not yet ready to assume, and this is the challenge to education in general (Vizconde, 2018). In the study of Barbarona, et. al., (2018) concluded in their study that pressure is a state of mental tension and worry that causes strong feelings. To overcome pressure and stress, there is a need to employ some strategies to alleviate threatening and stressful situations. These strategies are known as coping mechanisms. On the other hand, Tan (2017) concluded in his research findings that age is one of the significant predictors of faculty stress. Further, De Asis and Piczon (2019) revealed in their study investigating the stressors that affect teachers and identify the managing strategies they use in response to these stressors. Findings on the level of stress of the respondents revealed that more than 50 percent had a "high" level of stress on workload and role overload. "Average Level" on a relationship with learners, relationships with colleagues, and control of job environment. In terms of sources of stress of the respondents, findings showed that they were "very much stressed" with a lack of school facilities, lack of resources, completing forms, and paperwork. In the study of Andresio

(2020) it was concluded that the teachers of Maa District Division of Davao City contented with their job, they developed and maintained high level of performance. The age, highest educational attainments and length of service were significant to the job performance. Sex and civil status were noted to have a significant difference over career development. According to Tan (2017), several studies have shown a strong support for teachers getting stress with multiple reasons and causes. The fact is alarming,

since teachers should always carry the glamour of being positive in everything. If an individual is happy in his or her work, then the energy of doing the tasks is high. Anyone can be productive under convenient situations. The same in teaching, the root causes of stress among teachers might differ on certain conditions like for instance its location, intensity of job, organizational culture, and other demographic profile of individuals.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Deloy (2023), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Bedo (2022) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses pressure related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since it determines pressure related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in twelve (12) schools of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of

Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers. Random sampling technique will be employed in this study. However, Carmen Integrated School and Valencia Integrated School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study adapted a questionnaire on school environment which was patterned and adapted by the researcher from Theory of Transactional Model of Stress by Lazarus and Folkman's (1987) as cited by Quirido (2021). This view would sug-

gest that if the individual can perceive environmental and psychological demands made on him or her, he or she could learn for example, through counseling as a form of intervention to recognize which are the best resources to call upon when confronted with perceived stressful demands. Pressure or stress, itself, is an individual psychological state. It has to do with the person’s perception of the work environment and the emotional experience of it. This is supported by Self-efficacy or Effectiveness by Bandura (1994) which was cited by Opaon (2021). Teachers were motivated to be at their highest levels of effort and participation, maintained optimistic attitudes and thereby generated greater efficiency and work performance. Teacher performance evaluation plays a key role in educational personnel reform, so it has been an important yet difficult issue in educational reform. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher’s preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert’s opinions and pilot test-

ing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.694. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct had met the minimum reliability of 0.7342, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items on pressure-related issues with the following aspects relationships, career development, and home and work interface. Part 2 pertained to the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers with the dimensions, namely: instruction, classroom management and learner engagement. The perceptions of the respondents among the Cluster VI teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Pressure-related issues are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Pressure-related issues are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Pressure-related issues are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Pressure-related issues are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Pressure-related issues are not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—1. Permission to Conduct Study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public

Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answer-

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Self-effectiveness of teachers is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Self-effectiveness of teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Self-effectiveness of teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Self-effectiveness of teachers is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Self-effectiveness of teachers is not evident.

ing the questions and sent them back through researcher’s email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2023.

The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean. It was used to determine the extent of pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was

used in determining the significant components of pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant influence of components of pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of pressure-related issues in terms of relationships, career development, and home and work interface; the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in terms of instruction, classroom management, and learners engagement; and which factors of pressure-related issues significantly influence the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Pressure-Related Issues of Public Secondary Schools Teachers. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of pressure-related issues of public secondary school teachers. The indicator with highest mean is career development with a mean of (4.19), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by home and work interface has a mean

of (4,17) also identified as extensive. Lastly, relationships has the least mean of (4.16) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (4.17) or extensive, therefore, the summary on the pressure-related issues of public secondary school was extensive as perceived by the teachers.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Pressure-Related Issues of Public Secondary School Teachers

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Relationships	4.16	Extensive
2	Career Development	4.19	Extensive
3	Home and Work Interface	4.17	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.17	Extensive

It can be garnered from the table that career development, home and work interface, and relationships were extensive. Relationship was the least among the indicators of pressure-related issues of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Therefore, most of the respondents are a little bit pressured out when it comes to the way their learners and parents communicate with them. This implies that they encounter this kind of people, but it does not annoy them that much. The data bare a good manifestation that public secondary school teachers provide an understanding and democratic approaches to the parents and learners. Good leaders should possess an unwaver-

ing principle but with a heart and will always consider an open communication. Many parents do not support their students' education, which causes children to lose interest in their academics because their family does not support them. To the extent that teachers make every effort to contact parents and kids, especially if the learner is about to drop out of school. On the contrary, parents' lack of concern may be due to poverty; they do not have time to follow up on their children since they must first feed the family by working extremely hard before they can worry about other things, such as involvement in school.

Summary on the Extent of Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers. Displayed in Table 2 are the data on the summary on the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers. The indicators are presented from highest to lowest mean ratings given by the respondents. Classroom Management has a mean of (4.23) with a description of very extensive. Then, it followed by

instruction has gained a mean of (4.21) which also interpreted as very extensive. Finally, the respondents find learners engagement with a lowest mean of (4.16), which interpreted as extensive. It an overall generated mean of (4.20) or very extensive, therefore, the extent self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers was very extensive.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Instruction	4.21	Very Extensive
2	Classroom Management	4.23	Very Extensive
3	Learners Engagement	4.16	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.20	Very Extensive

The table shows that classroom management, instruction, and learners’ engagement were very extensive. Learners’ engagement was the least important determinant of public secondary school teachers’ self-effectiveness. Therefore, Learning is the product of trusting students to teachers. Establishing trust should start the moment the students enter the classroom. Lead a conversation with the class about how trust is important in all relationships as well as in learning. Through sharing experiences from teachers and learners can eventually lead to earning and demonstrating trust in the classroom. One of the challenges of learning relates to learners feeling disconnected to their classmates and instructor. By offering a variety of topics that are relevant to current issues in the field and allowing students to connect the practical, in this case their professional experience, to the theoretical, the course content, the learners become more invested in the course discussions and assignments, as well as their colleagues (Shearer, 2018). There are several affective factors related to learner engagement which include attitude, personality, motivation, effort, and self-confidence (Mandernach, et. al., 2011). Jaggars and Xu (2016) found that the quality of interaction within the course parameters positively correlated to learner grades in online courses. By evaluating the level of learner engagement and considering these affective aspects, instructors can more effectively

plan lessons and activities that will encourage learners to be more active participants in their learning and coursework. Learner engagement has also been described as the level of interest demonstrated by learners, how they interact with others in the course, and their motivation to learn about the topics (Briggs, 2015). Learner involvement is the energy and effort that learners put forth within their learning community, which can be measured using any variety of behavioral, cognitive, or affective indicators along a spectrum. A variety of structural and internal variables shape it, including the intricate interplay of connections, learning activities, and the learning environment. The more engaged and empowered learners are in their learning community, the more likely they are to channel that energy back into their learning, resulting in a variety of short and long term results that can also fuel engagement.

Significant Relationship Between the Pressure-Related Issues and Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Shown in table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.871. This means that there is a very strong negative significant relationship between the pressure-

related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies that an increasing manifesta-

tion pressure-related issues by the public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to the decrease of their self-effectiveness.

Table 1. Significant Relationship Between the Pressure-Related Issues and Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Self-Effectiveness of Teachers	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Pressure-Related Issues	-0.452	0.000	Reject
Relationship	-0.755	0.000	Reject
Career Development	-0.666	0.000	Reject
Home and Care Work Interface	-0.871	0.000	Reject
Overall	-0.871	0.000	Reject

Note: There is a moderate positive significant correlation (Relationship), strong positive significant correlation (Career Development, Home and Care Work Interface), and very strong positive significant correlation (Overall).

Particularly, the analysis in Table 3 highlighted also the association between each indicator of the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Based on the said analysis, the Career Development indicator of the pressure-related issues ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and $-r$ -value of -0.755. This result implies that there is a strong negative significant relationship between the career development indicator of the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that an increasing manifestation of career development pressure-related issues by the public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to the decrease of their self-effectiveness. This was followed by the Home and Care Work indicator of the pressure-related issues ranked as the top indicator with

a p-value of 0.000 and $-r$ -value of -0.666. Still, this means that there is a strong negative significant relationship between the home and care work indicator of the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that an increasing manifestation of home and care work pressure-related issues by the public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to the decrease of their self-effectiveness. Ranked last is the Relationship factor of indicator of the pressure-related issues ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and $-r$ -value of 0.452. This means that there is a moderate negative significant relationship between the relationship indicator of the pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that an increasing manifestation of relationship pressure-related issues by

the public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City leads to the decrease of their self-effectiveness. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Pressure-Related Issues on the Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis on the significant influence of the pressure-related issues on the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 323.985 which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the pressure-related issues has a significant influence on the self-effectiveness of public secondary school

teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that the regression analysis used in the study is useful which means that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. Relatively, the regression analysis as presented in the same table shows that there are two (2) out of the three (3) indicators of pressure-related issues significantly influenced the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. Therefore, the established null hypothesis of this study that there are no indicators of pressure-related issues that significantly influenced the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City is rejected.

Table 2. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Pressure-Related Issues on the Self-Effectiveness of Public Secondary School Teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City

Self-Effectiveness of Teachers	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho	
Constant	1.952	.080	24.398	.000		
Relationship	.217	.013	.477	16.563	.000	Reject
Career Development	.322	.028	.777	11.381	.000	Reject
Home and Care Work Interface	.013	.030	.006	1.087	.731	Reject

Note: R = 0.893, R² = 0.798, F-Value = 323.985, p-value = .000

Particularly, these pressure-related issues indicators that have significant influenced in accordance with their t-value were the Relationship indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 16.563 and a p-value equal to 0.000, and the Career Development indicator which obtained a t-value equal to 11.381 and a p-value equal to 0.000. On the other hand, the Home and Care Work Interface indicator of pressure-related issues does not significantly influence the pressure-related issues of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City with a t-value equal to 1.087 and p-value equal to 0.731. This numerical rating is considered lower than its set

critical value and higher than the set 0.05 alpha value. Furthermore, the regression analysis revealed an R-squared (R²) value of 0.798, signifying that 79.80 percent of the variation in the teachers' self-effectiveness of public secondary schools of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City is attributed to their pressure-related issues. In essence, this high (R²) value points to a significant relationship between the pressure-related issues and the self-effectiveness of teachers they adhere to. This data suggests that pressure-related issues are highly influential and should be considered crucial in self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. On the other side, the

remaining 20.20 percent of variation in self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City is not explained by the pressure-related issues as the variable being studied. This leaves room for other domains or indicators, not included in the current study, that may have an influential role in determining the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of pressure-related issues and the extent of self-effectiveness public secondary school teachers. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of pressure-related issues in terms of relationships, career development, and home and work interface. Moreover, this identified the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in terms of instruction, classroom management, and learners' engagement. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of pressure-related issues and the extent of self-effectiveness performance of public secondary school teachers. Using non-experimental research, the extent of pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public secondary school teachers in Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Theory of Transactional Model of Stress by Lazarus and Folkman's (1987) as cited by Quirido (2021) and Self-Efficacy of Effectiveness by Bandura (1994) as cited by Opaon (2021) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of pressure-related issues in terms of relationships, career development, and home and work interface was extensive. Similarly, the extent of self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers in terms of instruction, classroom management, and learners' engagement was very extensive which means that it was always manifested while in terms of pressure-related issues which extensive. Hence, the extent of self-effectiveness as demonstrated by public secondary school teachers of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City was very extensive. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 323.985 which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the pressure-related issues has a significant influence on the teachers' self-effectiveness of public secondary schools of Cluster VI, Division of Davao City. This further implies that the regression analysis used in the study is useful which means that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. Finally, indicators of pressure-related issues such as relationships and career development have significant influence on self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The pressure-related issues of public secondary school teachers was extensive. The self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers was very extensive. There was a strong positive relationship between pressure-related issues and self-effectiveness of public secondary

school teachers based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of pressure-related issues to the self-effectiveness of public secondary school teachers: Relationships and Career Development.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The school administration should have a system or program in place to regularly monitor teachers and administrators who are experiencing stress-related issues and to give services such as stress-reduction techniques to help them manage with pressure and enhance their quality of life. Teachers and school ad-

ministrators should have a good preparation and attitude towards teaching and of their respective relationships, career development, home and work interface to avoid pressure. Teachers should maintain a positive work outlook by responding to calls to duty with efficiency and timeliness, expressing oneself in terms of work-related challenges in order to gain administrative support and insights from colleagues, and actively participating in psychosocial wellness and professional development trainings. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimensions of the study.

5. References

- Allen, J. (2019). An interaction-based approach to enhancing secondary school instruction and student achievement. *Science*, 333(6045), 1034–1037.
- Alson, J. (2019). Stress among public school teachers. *Journal of Research Initiatives*, 4(2), 3.
- Barbarona, M. A. G., Barinan, R. R., Lagrada, C. M. D., Rances, K. M. L., Bolanio, I. C., Baay, J. O., & Baligat, V. M. (2018). Level of Stress and Coping Mechanisms of Teacher Education Interns of the University of Bohol. *Academe*, 12.
- Barnett, R. C., & Hyde, J. S. (2021). Women, men, work, and family. *American Psychologist*, 56(10), 781–796. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.56.10.781>
- Briggs, A. (2015). Ten ways to overcome barriers to student engagement online. Online Learning Consortium, Retrieved from http://onlinelearningconsortium.org/news_item/tenways-overcome-barriers-student-engagement-online/
- Brophy, J. (2016). History of research on classroom management. In C. M. Evertson & C. S. Weinstein (Eds.), *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues* (pp. 17- 43). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Bulatevych, N. (2017). Teacher's burnout syndrome: The Phenomenology of the process. *Polish Journal of Health* Vol.127, Issue 2 Zdrowie Publications, Poland pp. 63-64.
- Celik, B. (2017). Career Development of Teachers: Importance and Benefits. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 4(1), 131.
- Chen, Z (2019). Dynamics on the relationships among work and family resourcegain and loss, enrichment, and conflict over time. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 84(3), 293–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.02.006>
- Clark, L. (2019). Focus Group Research with Children and Youth. *Journal for Specialists in Pediatric Nursing*, 14, 152-154. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6155.2009.00187>.
- Coladarci, T. (2018). Teachers' sense of efficacy and commitment to teaching. *Journal of Education*, 323337. <http://doi.org/10.1080/00220973.1992.9943869>

- Cox, A., Solomon, B., & Parris, D. (2018). Teacher well-being is a critical and often overlooked part of school health. Child Trends Organization. <https://www.childtrends.org/teacher-well-being-is-a-critical-and-often-overlooked-part-of-school-health>.
- De Asis, L. A. & Piczon, V.A (2015). Sources and Level of Stress Coping Strategies of Faculty Members In The University Of Eastern Philippines. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* ISSN 2319-7064.1- 2. DOI: 10.21275/ART2017762
- Erdamar, G. (2016). Job and life satisfaction of teachers and the conflicts they experience at work and at home. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(6), 164–175. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v4i6.1502>.
- Emmer, E. (2019). Effective classroom management at the beginning of the school year. *Elementary School Journal*, 80, 219-231.
- Esguerra, I. D. G. (2020). Work-Life Balance and Job Stress of Employees of a Lone Agricultural College in Bulacan, Philippines. *Journal of Business on Hospitality and Tourism*, 6(2), 61-73.
- Friedlander, L. et.al., (2019). Social Support, Self-Esteem, and Stress as Predictors of Adjustment to University among First-Year Undergraduates. *Journal of College Student Development* 274. <https://doi.org/10.1353/csd.2007.0024>
- Froyen, L. (2019). *Schoolwide and classroom management: The reflective Educator leader* (3rd ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Garcia, A. S. (2018). Parental involvement among low-income Filipinos: A phenomenological inquiry
- Guskey, T. R. (2018) Staff development and teacher change, *Educational Leadership*, 42(7), 57- 60
- Iskra-Golec, I., et.al., (2016). Social and family issues in shift work and nonstandard working hours. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42286-2>.
- Jaggars, S. S., & Xu, Di (2016). How do online course design features influence student performance? *Computers and Education*, 95, 270-284, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2016.01.014
- Karavasilis, G. (2019). Work satisfaction or burnout and their impact on innovative work behavior of Greek teachers. *Journal of Contemporary Education Theory & Research (JCETR)*, 3(2), 3-10.

- Lazarus, Richard S., and Susan Folkman. "Transactional theory and research on emotions and coping." *European Journal of personality* 1, no. 3 (1987): 141-169.
- Mandemach, B. J., Domelli-Sallee, E., & Dailey-Hebert, A. (2011). Assessing course student engagement. In R. Miller, E. Amsel, B. M. Kowalewski, B.B. Beins, K. D. Keith, & B. F. Peden (Eds.), *Promoting Student Engagement: Techniques and Opportunities* (pp. 277- 281). Society for the Teaching of Psychology, Division 2, American Psychological Association.
- Marzano, R. et.al., (2021). *Classroom Instruction That Works*. Alexandria, Virginia: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Maedor, D. (2020). *School Issues That Negatively Impact Student Learning* Retrieved January 20,2021 from <https://www.thoughtco.com/issues-thatnegatively-impacts-student-learning-3194421>
- Mendelhall, M. (2017) *Teachers for teachers: professional development model for teachers in extraordinary circumstances*. Lecture, February 27, Teachers College, Columbia University
- Pianta, R. (2016). *Classroom* management and relationships between children and teacher: Implications for research and practice. In C. M. Evertson & C. S. Weinstein (Eds.), *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues* (pp. 685-710). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Robinson, S. (2016) *Helping individual students with problem behavior*. In C. M. Evertson & C. S. Weinstein (Eds.), *Handbook of classroom management: Research, practice, and contemporary issues* (pp. 787-802). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A. W. (2018). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive construct. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), 783–805. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X\(01\)00036-1](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0742-051X(01)00036-1)
- Sarabia, A., & Collantes, L. M. (2020). Work-related stress and teaching performance of teachers in selected school in the Philippines. | *IRJE| Indonesian Research Journal in Education*], 6-27.
- Shearer, R. L. (2018). *Interaction in distance education*. Special Report 2(1). Madison, WI: Atwood Publishing.

- Stuhlman, M., (2020). Developing and validating scalable approaches to assessing effective classroom interactions. Paper presented at the meeting of the American Educational Research Association, Vancouver, BC.
- Skaalvik, M. (2017). "Motivated for teaching? Associations with school goal structure, teacher self-efficacy, job satisfaction and emotional exhaustion." *Teaching and Teacher Education* 67: 152-160.
- Strong, M. (2019). Do we know a successful teacher when we see one? Experiments in the identification of effective teachers. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 62(4), 367–382.
- Struyven, K., et.al. (2018). Why do they want to teach? The multiple reasons of different groups of students for undertaking teacher education. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 28(3),1007–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-012-0151-4>.
- Tan, J. T. (2017). Factors Affecting Stress among Faculty Members of Public Universities in the Philippines: A Multiple Regression Analysis. *Canadian Center of Science and Education. International Journal of Psychological Studies*; Vol. 9, No. 3; 2017 ISSN 1918-7211 doi:10.5539/ijps.v9n3p64.
- Vizconde (2015). Issues, concerns, and prospects: teachers training institutions. 'Views on k-12. *Ejournal.ph* (Vol.9, No.1-2) ISSN 1908 9147.
- Vangie, M., et.al., (2019). Students, Peer Pressure and Their Academic Performance in School. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9, 301-312. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.9.01.2019.p8541>
- Yaacob, M. & Long, C.S. (2015). Role of Occupational Stress on Job Satisfaction. *Mediterranean Journal of So*
- Yusuf, F. A., Olufunke, Y. R., & Valentine, M. D. (2016). Causes and impact of stress on teachers' productivity as expressed by primary school teachers in Nigeria. *Creative Education*, 6(18), 1937.
- Zhang, M., Bai, Y., & Li, Z. (2020). Effect of Resilience on the Mental Health of Special Education Teachers: Moderating Effect of Teaching Barriers. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 13, 537